

Existence and uniqueness of best proximity point in non-Archimedean neutrosophic complete metric space

A. Sreelakshmi Unni¹ and V. Pragadeeswarar²

¹ Department of Mathematics, Amrita School of Physical Sciences Coimbatore, Amrita Vishwa Vidyapeetham, India; ua_sreelakshmi@cb.students.amrita.edu

² Department of Mathematics, Amrita School of Physical Sciences Coimbatore, Amrita Vishwa Vidyapeetham, India; v_pragadeeswarar@cb.amrita.edu

*Correspondence: v_pragadeeswarar@cb.amrita.edu

Abstract. This paper presents the concept of best proximity points for non-self mappings within the framework of non-Archimedean neutrosophic complete metric spaces. It also introduces two classes of mappings, namely neutrosophic proximal contractions of the first kind and the second kind, and establishes theorems guaranteeing the existence and uniqueness of best proximity points for these contractions.

1. Introduction

Neutrosophic metric spaces extend the concept of usual metric spaces by incorporating the idea of indeterminacy, which is essential for modeling uncertainty, vagueness, and incomplete information—features commonly encountered in real-world problems. Unlike classical metric spaces that rely on precise numerical distances, neutrosophic metric spaces allow for degrees of truth, falsity, and indeterminacy, making them highly suitable for applications in decision-making, artificial intelligence, and data analysis, where information is not always crisp or complete. This richer structure provides a more flexible and realistic mathematical framework for analyzing complex systems, especially in environments where traditional metrics fail to capture ambiguity and uncertainty effectively.

Smarandache [1] introduced neutrosophic logic and neutrosophic sets as an innovative generalization of classical set theory. These sets are characterized by three components: the degree of membership, the degree of indeterminacy, and the degree of non-membership. Building on this foundation, Kiriski et al. [2] formulated the concept of neutrosophic metric spaces (NMSs), and in [3], they established fixed point theorems in complete NMSs. Inspired by these developments, many researchers have explored generalized forms of NMSs and extended

classical fixed point theorems to this framework; see [4–10] for more information. Notably, Saleem et al. [6] extended fixed point theory to multivalued mappings and applied it to fractal settings, while in [8], Ishtiaq et al. introduced orthogonal NMSs and proved the existence of fixed points within that structure.

On the other hand, best proximity point theory plays a significant role in nonlinear analysis and optimization by offering solutions in cases where fixed points do not exist. In practical applications across fields like economics, engineering, and computer science, one often encounters mappings between two disjoint sets where a point cannot be mapped to itself. In such scenarios, best proximity point theory seeks points in one set that are nearest to their corresponding images in the other, effectively minimizing the distance between them. This approach extends classical fixed point theory and is essential for addressing constrained optimization problems, variational inequalities, and equilibrium models, where exact solutions are infeasible, yet the closest possible approximations are both useful and relevant.

Suppose M is a non-empty subset of a metric space (Ω, d) . A map $\Gamma : M \rightarrow \Omega$ is said to have a fixed point if $\Gamma x = x$ for some $x \in M$. Ky Fan provided an answer to the problem of finding a fixed point when the equation $\Gamma x = x$ does not have a solution, that is, $d(x, \Gamma x) > 0$ for all $x \in M$. In such a case, we must look for an element $x \in M$ such that $d(x, \Gamma x)$ is minimized. That is, let M_1, M_2 be two disjoint non-empty subsets of a metric space (Ω, d) and $\Gamma : M_1 \rightarrow M_2$ be a non-self map. Then Γ is said to have a best proximity point in M_1 if we can find an element $x \in M_1$ such that

$$d(x, \Gamma x) = d(M_1, M_2) = \inf\{d(a, b) : a \in M_1 \text{ and } b \in M_2\}.$$

Best proximity point theorems are studied to find the necessary conditions under which the minimization problem $\min_{x \in M_1} d(x, \Gamma x)$ has at least one solution. The existence and convergence of best proximity points is an interesting topic in optimization theory, which has recently attracted the attention of many authors [11–16]. A best proximity point theorem for non-self proximal contractions is investigated in [17–21].

Importance of best proximity point theory emerges when the fixed points do not exist. In our work, we consider neutrosophic metric spaces which is a generalisation of classical metric spaces and we extend the notion of best proximity point to this framework. There are studies on the existence of fixed point for a self map in the context of neutrosophic metric spaces but there are no works to date on the existence of best proximity points in neutrosophic metric spaces.

That is, in other words, the notion of a best proximity point for non-self mappings within neutrosophic complete metric spaces has not been formally introduced in the literature. In addition, the existence of a best proximity point for a non-self map in the setting of neutrosophic metric spaces has not yet been examined. In this work, we address this gap by establishing

both the existence and uniqueness of best proximity points for such mappings. As a result, we provide a foundational contribution to the theory of best proximity points in the context of neutrosophic metric spaces.

The paper is organized as follows. We begin by extending the concept of best proximity points and related notions to the framework of neutrosophic metric spaces. Next, we introduce two types of contractions: neutrosophic proximal contractions of the first kind and the second kind. Finally, we establish sufficient conditions under which a non-self mapping ensures the existence and uniqueness of best proximity points for both types of contractions. Consequently, we derive a proximal analogue of the Banach contraction principle within the setting of neutrosophic complete metric spaces.

2. Preliminaries:

Definition 2.1. [22] An operation $*$: $[0, 1] \times [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is a continuous t-norm (CTN) if $*$ satisfies conditions below:

- (I) $a * 1 = a$,
- (II) $*$ is commutative and associative
- (III) $*$ is continuous
- (IV) $a * b \leq u * v$ whenever $a \leq u$, $b \leq v$, and $a, b, u, v \in [0, 1]$.

Definition 2.2. [22] An operation \diamond : $[0, 1] \times [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is a continuous t-conorm (CTCN) if \diamond satisfies conditions below:

- (I) $a \diamond 0 = a$
- (II) \diamond is commutative and associative
- (III) \diamond is continuous
- (IV) $a \diamond b \leq u \diamond v$ whenever $a \leq u$ and $b \leq v$, and $a, b, u, v \in [0, 1]$.

Definition 2.3. [23] Suppose $R \neq \emptyset$. Given a six-tuple $(R, P_\phi, E_\phi, Z_\phi, *, \diamond)$ where $*$ is a continuous t-norm (CTN), \diamond is a continuous t-conorm (CTCN), and P_ϕ, E_ϕ, Z_ϕ are neutrosophic sets on $R \times R \times (0, \infty)$. If $(R, P_\phi, E_\phi, Z_\phi, *, \diamond)$ satisfies the conditions given below for all $u, v, r \in R$ and $\tau_1, \tau_2 > 0$:

- (I) $P_\phi(u, v, \tau_1) + E_\phi(u, v, \tau_1) + Z_\phi(u, v, \tau_1) \leq 3$
- (II) $0 \leq P_\phi(u, v, \tau_1) \leq 1$
- (III) $P_\phi(u, v, \tau_1) = 1 \iff u = v$
- (IV) $P_\phi(u, v, \tau_1) = P_\phi(v, u, \tau_1)$
- (V) $P_\phi(u, r, \tau_1 + \tau_2) \geq P_\phi(u, v, \tau_1) * P_\phi(v, r, \tau_2)$
- (VI) $P_\phi(u, v, \cdot) : [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is continuous
- (VII) $\lim_{\tau_1 \rightarrow \infty} P_\phi(u, v, \tau_1) = 1$

- (VIII) $0 \leq E_\phi(u, v, \tau_1) \leq 1$
- (IX) $E_\phi(u, v, \tau_1) = 0 \iff u = v$
- (X) $E_\phi(u, v, \tau_1) = E_\phi(v, u, \tau_1)$
- (XI) $E_\phi(u, r, \tau_1 + \tau_2) \leq E_\phi(u, v, \tau_1) \diamond E_\phi(v, r, \tau_2)$
- (XII) $E_\phi(u, v, \cdot) : [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is continuous
- (XIII) $\lim_{\tau_1 \rightarrow \infty} E_\phi(u, v, \tau_1) = 0$
- (XIV) $0 \leq Z_\phi(u, v, \tau_1) \leq 1$
- (XV) $Z_\phi(u, v, \tau_1) = 0 \iff u = v$
- (XVI) $Z_\phi(u, v, \tau_1) = Z_\phi(v, u, \tau_1)$
- (XVII) $Z_\phi(u, r, \tau_1 + \tau_2) \leq Z_\phi(u, v, \tau_1) \diamond Z_\phi(v, r, \tau_2)$
- (XVIII) $Z_\phi(u, v, \cdot) : [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is continuous
- (XIX) $\lim_{\tau_1 \rightarrow \infty} Z_\phi(u, v, \tau_1) = 0$
- (XX) If $\tau_1 \leq 0$, then $P_\phi(u, v, \tau_1) = 0$, $E_\phi(u, v, \tau_1) = 1$, and $Z_\phi(u, v, \tau_1) = 1$.

Then, (P_ϕ, E_ϕ, Z_ϕ) is a *neutrosophic metric* on R and $(R, P_\phi, E_\phi, Z_\phi, *, \diamond)$ is called a **neutrosophic metric space (NMS)**. The functions P_ϕ , E_ϕ , and Z_ϕ represent the degree of nearness, indeterminacy, and non-nearness, respectively.

- (XXI) $P_\phi(u, r, \tau) \geq P_\phi(u, v, \tau) * P_\phi(v, r, \tau)$
- (XXII) $E_\phi(u, r, \tau) \leq E_\phi(u, v, \tau) \diamond E_\phi(v, r, \tau)$
- (XXIII) $Z_\phi(u, r, \tau) \leq Z_\phi(u, v, \tau) \diamond Z_\phi(v, r, \tau)$.

Now, if we replace (V), (XI), (XVII) by (XXI), (XXII) and (XXIII), then $(R, P_\phi, E_\phi, Z_\phi, *, \diamond)$ is called a **non-Archimedean neutrosophic metric space (non-Archimedean NMS)**.

Here, note that $P_\phi(u, v, \tau)$ is non-decreasing with respect to τ . Similarly, both $E_\phi(u, v, t)$ and $Z_\phi(u, v, t)$ are non-increasing with respect to τ .

Example 2.4. [23] Let (R, Ω) be a metric space. Define the functions:

$$P_\phi(\omega_1, \omega_2, \tau) = \frac{\tau}{\tau + \Omega(\omega_1, \omega_2)}, E_\phi(\omega_1, \omega_2, \tau) = \frac{\Omega(\omega_1, \omega_2)}{\tau + \Omega(\omega_1, \omega_2)}, Z_\phi(\omega_1, \omega_2, \tau) = \frac{\Omega(\omega_1, \omega_2)}{\tau}$$

for all $\omega_1, \omega_2 \in R$ and $\tau > 0$. Then $(R, P_\phi, E_\phi, Z_\phi, *, \diamond)$ is called the *standard NMS* induced by the metric Ω .

Definition 2.5. [23] Let $(R, P_\phi, E_\phi, Z_\phi, *, \diamond)$ be a NMS. The open ball with center $\omega_1 \in R$, radius $0 < r < 1$, and parameter $\tau > 0$ is defined as:

$$B(\omega_1, r, \tau) = \{\omega_2 \in R : P_\phi(\omega_1, \omega_2, \tau) > 1 - r, E_\phi(\omega_1, \omega_2, \tau) < r, Z_\phi(\omega_1, \omega_2, \tau) < r\}$$

Define the topology:

$$\tau(P_\phi, E_\phi) = \{A \subset R : \forall \omega_1 \in A, \exists \tau > 0, r \in (0, 1) \text{ such that } B(\omega_1, r, \tau) \subset A\}.$$

Then $\tau(P_\phi, E_\phi)$ is the topology on R induced by the neutrosophic metric.

Definition 2.6. [23] Let $(R, P_\phi, E_\phi, Z_\phi, *, \diamond)$ be a NMS.

- a sequence $\{a_n\}$ in R is converging to a point $a \in R$ if for each $\tau > 0$, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} P_\phi(a_n, a, \tau) = 1$; $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} E_\phi(a_n, a, \tau) = 0$; $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Z_\phi(a_n, a, \tau) = 0$.
- a sequence $\{a_n\}$ in R is said to be Cauchy if for each $\epsilon > 0$ and $\tau > 0$, $\exists n_0 \in N$ such that $P_\phi(a_n, a_m, \tau) > 1 - \epsilon$; $E_\phi(a_n, a_m, \tau) < \epsilon$; $Z_\phi(a_n, a_m, \tau) < \epsilon$, $\forall n, m \leq n_0$.
- The space is said to be *complete* if every Cauchy sequence in R converges.
- The space is said to be *compact* if every sequence $\{a_n\}$ in R has a convergent subsequence $\{a_{n_k}\}$.

The notion of best proximity point for non-self mappings is follows.

Definition 2.7. Let (C, D) be a pair of two non-empty subsets of a neutrosophic metric space $(R, P_\phi, E_\phi, Z_\phi, *, \diamond)$. An element $x \in C$ is said to be a best proximity point of the non-self map $\Gamma : C \rightarrow D$ if it satisfies the conditions that $P_\phi(x, \Gamma x, \tau) = P_\phi(C, D, \tau)$, $E_\phi(x, \Gamma x, \tau) = E_\phi(C, D, \tau)$, and $Z_\phi(x, \Gamma x, \tau) = Z_\phi(C, D, \tau)$ for all $\tau > 0$.

Remark 2.8. In Definition 2.7, when $C = D$, we have $P_\phi(x, \Gamma x, \tau) = P_\phi(C, D, \tau) = 1$, $E_\phi(x, \Gamma x, \tau) = E_\phi(C, D, \tau) = 0$, and $Z_\phi(x, \Gamma x, \tau) = Z_\phi(C, D, \tau) = 0$ for all $\tau > 0$. That is, we obtain $x = \Gamma x$, a fixed point for the self-map Γ .

Given non-empty subsets C and D of a neutrosophic metric space $(R, P_\phi, E_\phi, Z_\phi, *, \diamond)$, the following notions are used subsequently:

$$\begin{aligned}
 P_\phi(C, D, \tau) &:= \sup\{P_\phi(x, y, \tau) : x \in C \text{ and } y \in D\} \\
 E_\phi(C, D, \tau) &:= \inf\{E_\phi(x, y, \tau) : x \in C \text{ and } y \in D\} \\
 Z_\phi(C, D, \tau) &:= \inf\{Z_\phi(x, y, \tau) : x \in C \text{ and } y \in D\}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 C_0(\tau) &= \left\{ x \in C \left| \begin{array}{l} P_\phi(x, y, \tau) = P_\phi(C, D, \tau), E_\phi(x, y, \tau) = E_\phi(C, D, \tau), \text{ and} \\ Z_\phi(x, y, \tau) = Z_\phi(C, D, \tau) \text{ for some } y \in D \end{array} \right. \right\} \\
 D_0(\tau) &= \left\{ y \in D \left| \begin{array}{l} P_\phi(x, y, \tau) = P_\phi(C, D, \tau), E_\phi(x, y, \tau) = E_\phi(C, D, \tau), \text{ and} \\ Z_\phi(x, y, \tau) = Z_\phi(C, D, \tau) \text{ for some } x \in C \end{array} \right. \right\}
 \end{aligned}$$

for all $\tau > 0$.

Definition 2.9. If every sequence $\{d_n\}$ in D satisfying the condition that $P_\phi(c, d_n, \tau) \rightarrow P_\phi(c, D, \tau)$, $E_\phi(c, d_n, \tau) \rightarrow E_\phi(c, D, \tau)$, and $Z_\phi(c, d_n, \tau) \rightarrow Z_\phi(c, D, \tau)$, for some c in C and for all $\tau > 0$ has a convergent subsequence, then the set D is said to be approximately compact with respect to C .

Note 2.10. Every compact set is approximately compact with respect to itself.

Example 2.11. Consider \mathbb{R} with the metric $d(x, y) = |x - y|$. Choose $C = [0, 1]$ and $D = [2, 3]$. Choose the CTN $*$ as $a * b = ab$ and the CCTN \diamond as $a \diamond b = \max\{a, b\}$. The functions $P_\phi, E_\phi, Z_\phi : \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R} \times [0, \infty)$ are defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} P_\phi(x, y, \tau) &= \frac{1}{1 + d(x, y)}, \\ E_\phi(x, y, \tau) &= \frac{d(x, y)}{1 + d(x, y)}, \\ Z_\phi(x, y, \tau) &= d(x, y), \end{aligned}$$

where $x, y \in \mathbb{R}$. Here, D is approximately compact with respect to C .

Now, here we define the notion of a neutrosophic proximal contraction maps as given below.

Definition 2.12. A mapping $\Gamma : C \rightarrow D$ is said to be a neutrosophic proximal contraction of first kind if there exists a non-negative number $k \in [0, 1)$ such that, for all u_1, u_2, x_1, x_2 in C ,

$$\left. \begin{aligned} P_\phi(u_1, \Gamma x_1, \tau) &= P_\phi(C, D, \tau) \\ P_\phi(u_2, \Gamma x_2, \tau) &= P_\phi(C, D, \tau) \end{aligned} \right\} \implies P_\phi(u_1, u_2, k\tau) \geq P_\phi(x_1, x_2, \tau)$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} E_\phi(u_1, \Gamma x_1, \tau) &= E_\phi(C, D, \tau) \\ E_\phi(u_2, \Gamma x_2, \tau) &= E_\phi(C, D, \tau) \end{aligned} \right\} \implies E_\phi(u_1, u_2, k\tau) \leq E_\phi(x_1, x_2, \tau)$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} Z_\phi(u_1, \Gamma x_1, \tau) &= Z_\phi(C, D, \tau) \\ Z_\phi(u_2, \Gamma x_2, \tau) &= Z_\phi(C, D, \tau) \end{aligned} \right\} \implies Z_\phi(u_1, u_2, k\tau) \leq Z_\phi(x_1, x_2, \tau)$$

for all $\tau > 0$.

Definition 2.13. A mapping $\Gamma : C \rightarrow D$ is said to be a neutrosophic proximal contraction of second kind if there exists a non-negative number $k \in [0, 1)$ such that, for all u_1, u_2, x_1, x_2 in C ,

$$\left. \begin{aligned} P_\phi(u_1, \Gamma x_1, \tau) &= P_\phi(C, D, \tau) \\ P_\phi(u_2, \Gamma x_2, \tau) &= P_\phi(C, D, \tau) \end{aligned} \right\} \implies P_\phi(\Gamma u_1, \Gamma u_2, k\tau) \geq P_\phi(\Gamma x_1, \Gamma x_2, \tau)$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} E_\phi(u_1, \Gamma x_1, \tau) &= E_\phi(C, D, \tau) \\ E_\phi(u_2, \Gamma x_2, \tau) &= E_\phi(C, D, \tau) \end{aligned} \right\} \implies E_\phi(\Gamma u_1, \Gamma u_2, k\tau) \leq E_\phi(\Gamma x_1, \Gamma x_2, \tau)$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} Z_\phi(u_1, \Gamma x_1, \tau) &= Z_\phi(C, D, \tau) \\ Z_\phi(u_2, \Gamma x_2, \tau) &= Z_\phi(C, D, \tau) \end{aligned} \right\} \implies Z_\phi(\Gamma u_1, \Gamma u_2, k\tau) \leq Z_\phi(\Gamma x_1, \Gamma x_2, \tau)$$

for all $\tau > 0$.

3. Main Results:

Here, we prove the existence of the best proximity point for a given non-self map in a non-Archimedean neutrosophic complete metric space.

Theorem 3.1. *Let (C, D) be a pair of non-empty closed subsets of a non-Archimedean neutrosophic complete metric space $(R, P_\phi, E_\phi, Z_\phi, *, \diamond)$ such that C_0 is non-empty and D is approximately compact with respect to C . Let $\Gamma : C \rightarrow D$ be a map satisfying the following conditions:*

- (i) Γ is a neutrosophic proximal contraction of first kind;
- (ii) $\Gamma(C_0) \subseteq D_0$.

Then, there exists a unique best proximity point $x \in C$ for Γ . That is, $P_\phi(x, \Gamma x, \tau) = P_\phi(C, D, \tau)$, $E_\phi(x, \Gamma x, \tau) = E_\phi(C, D, \tau)$, and $Z_\phi(x, \Gamma x, \tau) = Z_\phi(C, D, \tau)$. Further, for any fixed element $u_0 \in C_0$, the sequence $\{u_n\}$, defined by $P_\phi(u_{n+1}, \Gamma u_n, \tau) = P_\phi(C, D, \tau)$, $E_\phi(u_{n+1}, \Gamma u_n, \tau) = E_\phi(C, D, \tau)$, and $Z_\phi(u_{n+1}, \Gamma u_n, \tau) = Z_\phi(C, D, \tau)$ converges to the element x .

Proof. Step 1: Construction of the sequence $\{u_n\}$.

Choose $u_0 \in C_0$. Since $\Gamma u_0 \in \Gamma(C_0) \subseteq D_0$, there exists $u_1 \in C_0$ such that $P_\phi(u_1, \Gamma u_0, \tau) = P_\phi(C, D, \tau)$, $E_\phi(u_1, \Gamma u_0, \tau) = E_\phi(C, D, \tau)$, and $Z_\phi(u_1, \Gamma u_0, \tau) = Z_\phi(C, D, \tau)$. Since $\Gamma u_1 \in \Gamma(C_0) \subseteq D_0$, there exists $u_2 \in C_0$ such that $P_\phi(u_2, \Gamma u_1, \tau) = P_\phi(C, D, \tau)$, $E_\phi(u_2, \Gamma u_1, \tau) = E_\phi(C, D, \tau)$, and $Z_\phi(u_2, \Gamma u_1, \tau) = Z_\phi(C, D, \tau)$. Continuing this process, we can find a sequence $\{u_n\}$ in C_0 such that

$$\left. \begin{aligned} P_\phi(u_{n+1}, \Gamma u_n, \tau) &= P_\phi(C, D, \tau), \\ E_\phi(u_{n+1}, \Gamma u_n, \tau) &= E_\phi(C, D, \tau), \\ Z_\phi(u_{n+1}, \Gamma u_n, \tau) &= Z_\phi(C, D, \tau), \quad \forall n \in \mathbb{N}. \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{1}$$

If there exists n_0 such that $u_{n_0} = u_{n_0+1}$, then $P_\phi(u_{n_0}, \Gamma u_{n_0}, \tau) = P_\phi(C, D, \tau)$, $E_\phi(u_{n_0}, \Gamma u_{n_0}, \tau) = E_\phi(C, D, \tau)$, and $Z_\phi(u_{n_0}, \Gamma u_{n_0}, \tau) = Z_\phi(C, D, \tau)$. This means that u_{n_0} is a best proximity point of Γ and the proof is finished. Thus, we can suppose that $u_n \neq u_{n+1}$ for all n .

Claim 1: Sequence $\{u_n\}$ is Cauchy.

Since Γ is a neutrosophic proximal contraction of first kind, it follows that

$$\left. \begin{aligned} P_\phi(u_{n+1}, u_n, k\tau) &\geq P_\phi(u_n, u_{n-1}, \tau), \\ E_\phi(u_{n+1}, u_n, k\tau) &\leq E_\phi(u_n, u_{n-1}, \tau), \\ Z_\phi(u_{n+1}, u_n, k\tau) &\leq Z_\phi(u_n, u_{n-1}, \tau), \quad \forall n \in \mathbb{N}. \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{2}$$

By Mathematical induction, we have

$$\left. \begin{aligned} P_\phi(u_{n+1}, u_n, \tau) &\geq P_\phi(u_0, u_1, \frac{\tau}{k^n}), \\ E_\phi(u_{n+1}, u_n, \tau) &\leq E_\phi(u_0, u_1, \frac{\tau}{k^n}), \\ Z_\phi(u_{n+1}, u_n, \tau) &\leq Z_\phi(u_0, u_1, \frac{\tau}{k^n}), \quad \forall n \in \mathbb{N} \text{ and } k \in (0, 1). \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{3}$$

Thus for any positive integer q , we have

$$\left. \begin{aligned} P_\phi(u_{n+q}, u_n, \tau) &\geq P_\phi(u_n, u_{n+1}, \tau) * \dots \text{(q-times)} \dots * P_\phi(u_{n+q-1}, u_{n+q}, \tau) \\ &\geq P_\phi(u_n, u_{n+1}, \frac{\tau}{q}) * \dots \text{(q-times)} \dots * P_\phi(u_{n+q-1}, u_{n+q}, \frac{\tau}{q}) \\ &\geq P_\phi(u_0, u_1, \frac{\tau}{qk^n}) * \dots \text{(q-times)} \dots * P_\phi(u_0, u_1, \frac{\tau}{qk^{n+q-1}}), \\ E_\phi(u_{n+q}, u_n, \tau) &\leq E_\phi(u_n, u_{n+1}, \tau) \diamond \dots \text{(q-times)} \dots \diamond E_\phi(u_{n+q-1}, u_{n+q}, \tau) \\ &\leq E_\phi(u_n, u_{n+1}, \frac{\tau}{q}) \diamond \dots \text{(q-times)} \dots \diamond E_\phi(u_{n+q-1}, u_{n+q}, \frac{\tau}{q}) \\ &\leq E_\phi(u_0, u_1, \frac{\tau}{qk^n}) \diamond \dots \text{(q-times)} \dots \diamond E_\phi(u_0, u_1, \frac{\tau}{qk^{n+q-1}}), \\ Z_\phi(u_{n+q}, u_n, \tau) &\leq Z_\phi(u_n, u_{n+1}, \tau) \diamond \dots \text{(q-times)} \dots \diamond Z_\phi(u_{n+q-1}, u_{n+q}, \tau) \\ &\leq Z_\phi(u_n, u_{n+1}, \frac{\tau}{q}) \diamond \dots \text{(q-times)} \dots \diamond Z_\phi(u_{n+q-1}, u_{n+q}, \frac{\tau}{q}) \\ &\leq Z_\phi(u_0, u_1, \frac{\tau}{qk^n}) \diamond \dots \text{(q-times)} \dots \diamond Z_\phi(u_0, u_1, \frac{\tau}{qk^{n+q-1}}). \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{4}$$

Now by (4) and the definition of NMS conditions, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} P_\phi(u_{n+q}, u_n, \tau) &\geq 1 * \dots \text{(q-times)} \dots * 1 = 1, \\ \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} E_\phi(u_{n+q}, u_n, \tau) &\leq 0 \diamond \dots \text{(q-times)} \dots \diamond 0 = 0, \\ \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Z_\phi(u_{n+q}, u_n, \tau) &\leq 0 \diamond \dots \text{(q-times)} \dots \diamond 0 = 0. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, $\{u_n\}$ is a Cauchy sequence in C .

Step 2: Establishing the existence of the best proximity point.

Since $\{u_n\}$ is a Cauchy sequence in C it converges to some element $x \in C$.

$$\left. \begin{aligned} P_\phi(x, D, \tau) &\geq P_\phi(x, \Gamma u_n, \tau), \\ &\geq P_\phi(x, u_{n+1}, \tau) * P_\phi(u_{n+1}, \Gamma u_n, \tau), \\ &= P_\phi(x, u_{n+1}, \tau) * P_\phi(C, D, \tau), \\ &\geq P_\phi(x, u_{n+1}, \tau) * P_\phi(x, D, \tau). \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{5}$$

Also,

$$\left. \begin{aligned} E_\phi(x, D, \tau) &\leq E_\phi(x, \Gamma u_n, \tau), \\ &\leq E_\phi(x, u_{n+1}, \tau) \diamond E_\phi(u_{n+1}, \Gamma u_n, \tau), \\ &= E_\phi(x, u_{n+1}, \tau) \diamond E_\phi(C, D, \tau), \\ &\leq E_\phi(x, u_{n+1}, \tau) \diamond E_\phi(x, D, \tau). \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{6}$$

Similarly,

$$\left. \begin{aligned} Z_\phi(x, D, \tau) &\leq Z_\phi(x, \Gamma u_n, \tau), \\ &\leq Z_\phi(x, u_{n+1}, \tau) \diamond Z_\phi(u_{n+1}, \Gamma u_n, \tau), \\ &= Z_\phi(x, u_{n+1}, \tau) \diamond Z_\phi(C, D, \tau), \\ &\leq Z_\phi(x, u_{n+1}, \tau) \diamond Z_\phi(x, D, \tau). \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{7}$$

From (5),(6) and (7), we get $P_\phi(x, \Gamma u_n, \tau) \rightarrow P_\phi(x, D, \tau), E_\phi(x, \Gamma u_n, \tau) \rightarrow E_\phi(x, D, \tau)$ and $Z_\phi(x, \Gamma u_n, \tau) \rightarrow Z_\phi(x, D, \tau)$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Since D is approximatively compact with respect to C , $\{\Gamma u_n\}$ has a convergent subsequence $\{\Gamma u_{n_k}\}$, converging to some $y \in D$. Hence we can conclude that

$$\begin{aligned} P_\phi(x, y, \tau) &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} P_\phi(u_{n_k+1}, \Gamma u_{n_k}, \tau) = P_\phi(C, D, \tau), \\ E_\phi(x, y, \tau) &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} E_\phi(u_{n_k+1}, \Gamma u_{n_k}, \tau) = E_\phi(C, D, \tau), \\ Z_\phi(x, y, \tau) &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Z_\phi(u_{n_k+1}, \Gamma u_{n_k}, \tau) = Z_\phi(C, D, \tau). \end{aligned}$$

That is $x \in C_0$. Since $\Gamma C_0 \subseteq D_0$, there exist $u \in C$ such that

$$\left. \begin{aligned} P_\phi(u, \Gamma x, \tau) &= P_\phi(C, D, \tau), \\ E_\phi(u, \Gamma x, \tau) &= E_\phi(C, D, \tau), \\ Z_\phi(u, \Gamma x, \tau) &= Z_\phi(C, D, \tau). \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{8}$$

Applying that Γ is a neutrosophic contraction of first kind to (1) and (8), we obtain

$$\left. \begin{aligned} P_\phi(u_{n+1}, u, k\tau) &\geq P_\phi(u_n, x, \tau), \\ E_\phi(u_{n+1}, u, k\tau) &\leq E_\phi(u_n, x, \tau), \\ Z_\phi(u_{n+1}, u, k\tau) &\leq Z_\phi(u_n, x, \tau), \quad \forall n \in \mathbb{N}. \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{9}$$

By the definition of neutrosophic metric and using $u_n \rightarrow x$ in (9), we get

$$\left. \begin{aligned} 1 &\geq P_\phi(x, u, k\tau) \geq P_\phi(x, x, \tau) = 1, \\ 0 &\leq E_\phi(x, u, k\tau) \leq E_\phi(x, x, \tau) = 0, \\ 0 &\leq Z_\phi(x, u, k\tau) \leq Z_\phi(x, x, \tau) = 0. \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{10}$$

Hence, we obtain $x = u$. From (8), it follows that x is a best proximity point for Γ .

Claim 2: Best proximity point of Γ is unique.

Suppose we can find another element $z \in C$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} P_\phi(z, \Gamma z, \tau) &= P_\phi(C, D, \tau), \\ E_\phi(z, \Gamma z, \tau) &= E_\phi(C, D, \tau), \\ Z_\phi(z, \Gamma z, \tau) &= Z_\phi(C, D, \tau). \end{aligned}$$

Since Γ is a neutrosophic proximal contraction of first kind, for every $\tau \in (0, \infty)$ and fixed $k \in (0, 1)$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} P_\phi(x, z, k\tau) &\geq P_\phi(x, z, \tau), \\ E_\phi(x, z, k\tau) &\leq E_\phi(x, z, \tau), \\ Z_\phi(x, z, k\tau) &\leq Z_\phi(x, z, \tau). \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, we get

$$\begin{aligned} 1 &\geq P_\phi(x, z, \tau) \geq P_\phi\left(x, z, \frac{\tau}{k}\right) \geq P_\phi\left(x, z, \frac{\tau}{k^2}\right) \\ &\geq \dots \geq P_\phi\left(x, z, \frac{\tau}{k^n}\right) \rightarrow 1 \quad \text{as } n \rightarrow \infty, \\ 0 &\leq E_\phi(x, z, \tau) \leq E_\phi\left(x, z, \frac{\tau}{k}\right) \leq E_\phi\left(x, z, \frac{\tau}{k^2}\right) \\ &\leq \dots \leq E_\phi\left(x, z, \frac{\tau}{k^n}\right) \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } n \rightarrow \infty, \\ 0 &\leq Z_\phi(x, z, \tau) \leq Z_\phi\left(x, z, \frac{\tau}{k}\right) \leq Z_\phi\left(x, z, \frac{\tau}{k^2}\right) \\ &\leq \dots \leq Z_\phi\left(x, z, \frac{\tau}{k^n}\right) \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } n \rightarrow \infty. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, by the definition of a neutrosophic metric space (NMS), we obtain $x = z$. Therefore, Γ has a **unique best proximity point**. \square

Now, we provide an example to demonstrate Theorem 3.1.

Example 3.2. Consider \mathbb{R}^2 with the metric $d((x_1, y_1), (x_2, y_2)) = |x_1 - x_2| + |y_1 - y_2|$. Choose $C = \{0\} \times \mathbb{R}$ and $D = \{1\} \times \mathbb{R}$. Define $\Gamma : C \rightarrow D$ as $\Gamma(0, x) = (1, \frac{x}{4})$. Choose the CTN $*$ as $a * b = ab$ and the CCTN \diamond as $a \diamond b = \max\{a, b\}$. The functions $P_\phi, E_\phi, Z_\phi : \mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2 \times [0, \infty)$ are defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} P_\phi(z_i, z_{i+1}, \tau) &= \frac{1}{1 + d(z_i, z_{i+1})}, \\ E_\phi(z_i, z_{i+1}, \tau) &= \frac{d(z_i, z_{i+1})}{1 + d(z_i, z_{i+1})}, \\ Z_\phi(z_i, z_{i+1}, \tau) &= d(z_i, z_{i+1}), \end{aligned}$$

where $z_i = (x_i, y_i)$ and $z_{i+1} = (x_{i+1}, y_{i+1})$, for $x_i, y_i, x_{i+1}, y_{i+1} \in \mathbb{R}$.

We have

$$\begin{aligned} P_\phi(C, D, \tau) &= \frac{1}{2}, \\ E_\phi(C, D, \tau) &= \frac{1}{2}, \\ Z_\phi(C, D, \tau) &= 1, \quad \tau > 0. \end{aligned}$$

Claim: Γ is a neutrosophic proximal contraction of the first kind.

Step 1: Suppose we have $(0, u_1), (0, u_2), (0, x_1), (0, x_2) \in C$ such that

$$P_\phi((0, u_1), \Gamma(0, x_1), \tau) = P_\phi(C, D, \tau) = \frac{1}{2} = P_\phi((0, u_2), \Gamma(0, x_2), \tau).$$

We have to verify that $P_\phi((0, u_1), (0, u_2), k\tau) \geq P_\phi((0, x_1), (0, x_2), \tau)$ for some $k \in [0, 1)$.

Then $u_1 = \frac{x_1}{4}$ and $u_2 = \frac{x_2}{4}$, for all $(0, x_1), (0, x_2) \in C$. Now, consider

$$P_\phi((0, u_1), (0, u_2), k\tau) = \frac{1}{1 + |u_1 - u_2|},$$

and

$$P_\phi((0, x_1), (0, x_2), \tau) = \frac{1}{1 + |x_1 - x_2|} = \frac{1}{1 + 4|u_1 - u_2|}.$$

Hence, it holds for any $k \in [0, 1)$.

Step 2: Suppose we have $(0, u_1), (0, u_2), (0, x_1), (0, x_2) \in C$ such that

$$E_\phi((0, u_1), \Gamma(0, x_1), \tau) = E_\phi(C, D, \tau) = \frac{1}{2} = E_\phi((0, u_2), \Gamma(0, x_1), \tau).$$

We have to verify that $E_\phi((0, u_1), (0, u_2), k\tau) \leq E_\phi((0, x_1), (0, x_2), \tau)$ for some $k \in [0, 1)$.

Then $u_1 = \frac{x_1}{4}$ and $u_2 = \frac{x_2}{4}$, for all $(0, x_1), (0, x_2) \in C$. Now, consider

$$E_\phi((0, u_1), (0, u_2), k\tau) = \frac{|u_1 - u_2|}{1 + |u_1 - u_2|},$$

and

$$E_\phi((0, x_1), (0, x_2), \tau) = \frac{|x_1 - x_2|}{1 + |x_1 - x_2|} = \frac{4|u_1 - u_2|}{1 + 4|u_1 - u_2|}.$$

Hence, it holds for any $k \in [0, 1)$.

Step 3: Suppose we have $(0, u_1), (0, u_2), (0, x_1), (0, x_2) \in C$ such that

$$Z_\phi((0, u_1), \Gamma(0, x_1), \tau) = Z_\phi(C, D, \tau) = 1 = Z_\phi((0, u_2), \Gamma(0, x_2), \tau).$$

We have to verify that $Z_\phi((0, u_1), (0, u_2), k\tau) \leq Z_\phi((0, x_1), (0, x_2), \tau)$ for some $k \in [0, 1)$.

Then $u_1 = \frac{x_1}{4}$ and $u_2 = \frac{x_2}{4}$, for all $(0, x_1), (0, x_2) \in C$. Now, consider

$$Z_\phi((0, u_1), (0, u_2), k\tau) = |u_1 - u_2|,$$

and

$$Z_\phi((0, x_1), (0, x_2), \tau) = |x_1 - x_2| = 4|u_1 - u_2|.$$

Hence, it holds for any $k \in [0, 1)$.

Thus, Γ is a neutrosophic proximal contraction of the first kind. Now, by Theorem 3.1, Γ has a unique best proximity point $(0, 0)$ in C .

Next, we are going to prove the existence and uniqueness of the best proximity point for a contraction different from the one employed in Theorem 3.1.

Theorem 3.3. *Let (C, D) be a pair of non-empty closed subsets of a non-Archimedean neutrosophic complete metric space $(R, P_\phi, E_\phi, Z_\phi, *, \diamond)$ such that C_0 is non-empty and C is approximately compact with respect to D . Let $\Gamma : C \rightarrow D$ be a map satisfying the conditions given below:*

- (i) Γ is a continuous neutrosophic proximal contraction of second kind;
- (ii) $\Gamma(C_0) \subseteq D_0$.

Then, there exists a best proximity point $z \in C$ for Γ . That is, $P_\phi(z, \Gamma z, \tau) = P_\phi(C, D, \tau)$, $E_\phi(z, \Gamma z, \tau) = E_\phi(C, D, \tau)$, and $Z_\phi(z, \Gamma z, \tau) = Z_\phi(C, D, \tau)$. Further, for any fixed element $u_0 \in C_0$, the sequence $\{u_n\}$, defined by $P_\phi(u_{n+1}, \Gamma u_n, \tau) = P_\phi(C, D, \tau)$, $E_\phi(u_{n+1}, \Gamma u_n, \tau) = E_\phi(C, D, \tau)$, and $Z_\phi(u_{n+1}, \Gamma u_n, \tau) = Z_\phi(C, D, \tau)$ has a subsequence $\{u_{n_k}\}$ that converges to the element z . Moreover, if z^* is another best proximity point of Γ , then $\Gamma z = \Gamma z^*$; hence, Γ is constant on the set of all best proximity points of Γ .

Proof. Following the proof of Theorem 3.1, we can find a sequence $\{u_n\}$ in C satisfying the following conditions:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} P_\phi(u_{n+1}, \Gamma u_n, \tau) &= P_\phi(C, D, \tau), \\ E_\phi(u_{n+1}, \Gamma u_n, \tau) &= E_\phi(C, D, \tau), \\ Z_\phi(u_{n+1}, \Gamma u_n, \tau) &= Z_\phi(C, D, \tau), \quad \forall n \in \mathbb{N}. \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{11}$$

If we can find n_0 such that $u_{n_0} = u_{n_0+1}$, then $P_\phi(u_{n_0}, \Gamma u_{n_0}, \tau) = P_\phi(C, D, \tau)$, $E_\phi(u_{n_0}, \Gamma u_{n_0}, \tau) = E_\phi(C, D, \tau)$, and $Z_\phi(u_{n_0}, \Gamma u_{n_0}, \tau) = Z_\phi(C, D, \tau)$. This means that u_{n_0} is a best proximity point of Γ and the proof is finished. Thus, we can suppose that $u_n \neq u_{n+1}$ for all n .

Claim 1: Sequence $\{u_n\}$ is Cauchy.

Since Γ is a neutrosophic proximal contraction of second kind, it we obtain that

$$\left. \begin{aligned} P_\phi(\Gamma u_{n+1}, \Gamma u_n, k\tau) &\geq P_\phi(\Gamma u_n, \Gamma u_{n-1}, \tau), \\ E_\phi(\Gamma u_{n+1}, \Gamma u_n, k\tau) &\leq E_\phi(\Gamma u_n, \Gamma u_{n-1}, \tau), \\ Z_\phi(\Gamma u_{n+1}, \Gamma u_n, k\tau) &\leq Z_\phi(\Gamma u_n, \Gamma u_{n-1}, \tau), \quad \forall n \in \mathbb{N}. \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{12}$$

By Mathematical induction, we obtain

$$\left. \begin{aligned} P_\phi(\Gamma u_{n+1}, \Gamma u_n, \tau) &\geq P_\phi(\Gamma u_0, \Gamma u_1, \frac{\tau}{k^n}), \\ E_\phi(\Gamma u_{n+1}, \Gamma u_n, \tau) &\leq E_\phi(\Gamma u_0, \Gamma u_1, \frac{\tau}{k^n}), \\ Z_\phi(\Gamma u_{n+1}, \Gamma u_n, \tau) &\leq Z_\phi(\Gamma u_0, \Gamma u_1, \frac{\tau}{k^n}), \quad \forall n \in \mathbb{N} \text{ and } k \in (0, 1). \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{13}$$

Thus for any positive integer q , we get

$$\left. \begin{aligned}
 P_\phi(\Gamma u_{n+q}, \Gamma u_n, \tau) &\geq P_\phi(\Gamma u_n, \Gamma u_{n+1}, \tau) * \cdots \text{(q-times)} \cdots * P_\phi(\Gamma u_{n+q-1}, \Gamma u_{n+q}, \tau) \\
 &\geq P_\phi(\Gamma u_n, \Gamma u_{n+1}, \frac{\tau}{q}) * \cdots \text{(q-times)} \cdots * P_\phi(\Gamma u_{n+q-1}, \Gamma u_{n+q}, \frac{\tau}{q}) \\
 &\geq P_\phi(\Gamma u_0, \Gamma u_1, \frac{\tau}{q^{k^n}}) * \cdots \text{(q-times)} \cdots * P_\phi(\Gamma u_0, \Gamma u_1, \frac{\tau}{q^{k^{n+q-1}}}), \\
 E_\phi(\Gamma u_{n+q}, \Gamma u_n, \tau) &\leq E_\phi(\Gamma u_n, \Gamma u_{n+1}, \tau) \diamond \cdots \text{(q-times)} \cdots \diamond E_\phi(\Gamma u_{n+q-1}, \Gamma u_{n+q}, \tau) \\
 &\leq E_\phi(\Gamma u_n, \Gamma u_{n+1}, \frac{\tau}{q}) \diamond \cdots \text{(q-times)} \cdots \diamond E_\phi(\Gamma u_{n+q-1}, \Gamma u_{n+q}, \frac{\tau}{q}) \\
 &\leq E_\phi(\Gamma u_0, \Gamma u_1, \frac{\tau}{q^{k^n}}) \diamond \cdots \text{(q-times)} \cdots \diamond E_\phi(\Gamma u_0, \Gamma u_1, \frac{\tau}{q^{k^{n+q-1}}}), \\
 Z_\phi(\Gamma u_{n+q}, \Gamma u_n, \tau) &\leq Z_\phi(\Gamma u_n, \Gamma u_{n+1}, \tau) \diamond \cdots \text{(q-times)} \cdots \diamond Z_\phi(\Gamma u_{n+q-1}, \Gamma u_{n+q}, \tau) \\
 &\leq Z_\phi(\Gamma u_n, \Gamma u_{n+1}, \frac{\tau}{q}) \diamond \cdots \text{(q-times)} \cdots \diamond Z_\phi(\Gamma u_{n+q-1}, \Gamma u_{n+q}, \frac{\tau}{q}) \\
 &\leq Z_\phi(\Gamma u_0, \Gamma u_1, \frac{\tau}{q^{k^n}}) \diamond \cdots \text{(q-times)} \cdots \diamond Z_\phi(\Gamma u_0, \Gamma u_1, \frac{\tau}{q^{k^{n+q-1}}}).
 \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{14}$$

Now by (14) and the definition of NMS conditions, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} P_\phi(\Gamma u_{n+q}, \Gamma u_n, \tau) &\geq 1 * \cdots \text{(q-times)} \cdots * 1 = 1, \\
 \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} E_\phi(\Gamma u_{n+q}, \Gamma u_n, \tau) &\leq 0 \diamond \cdots \text{(q-times)} \cdots \diamond 0 = 0, \\
 \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Z_\phi(\Gamma u_{n+q}, \Gamma u_n, \tau) &\leq 0 \diamond \cdots \text{(q-times)} \cdots \diamond 0 = 0.
 \end{aligned}$$

Thus, $\{\Gamma u_n\}$ is a Cauchy sequence in D .

Claim 2: Γ has a best proximity point in D .

Since $\{\Gamma u_n\}$ is a Cauchy sequence in D , it converges to some element $y \in D$. Now,

$$\left. \begin{aligned}
 P_\phi(y, C, \tau) &\geq P_\phi(y, u_n, \tau), \\
 &\geq P_\phi(y, \Gamma u_{n-1}, \tau) * P_\phi(\Gamma u_{n-1}, u_n, \tau), \\
 &= P_\phi(y, \Gamma u_{n-1}, \tau) * P_\phi(C, D, \tau), \\
 &\geq P_\phi(y, \Gamma u_{n-1}, \tau) * P_\phi(y, C, \tau).
 \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{15}$$

Also,

$$\left. \begin{aligned}
 E_\phi(y, C, \tau) &\leq E_\phi(y, u_n, \tau), \\
 &\leq E_\phi(y, \Gamma u_{n-1}, \tau) \diamond E_\phi(\Gamma u_{n-1}, u_n, \tau), \\
 &= E_\phi(y, \Gamma u_{n-1}, \tau) \diamond E_\phi(C, D, \tau), \\
 &\leq E_\phi(y, \Gamma u_{n-1}, \tau) \diamond E_\phi(y, C, \tau).
 \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{16}$$

Similarly,

$$\left. \begin{aligned}
 Z_\phi(y, C, \tau) &\leq Z_\phi(y, u_n, \tau), \\
 &\leq Z_\phi(y, \Gamma u_{n-1}, \tau) \diamond Z_\phi(\Gamma u_{n-1}, u_n, \tau), \\
 &= E_\phi(y, \Gamma u_{n-1}, \tau) \diamond Z_\phi(C, D, \tau), \\
 &\leq Z_\phi(y, \Gamma u_{n-1}, \tau) \diamond Z_\phi(y, C, \tau).
 \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{17}$$

From (15),(16) and (17), we get $P_\phi(y, u_n, \tau) \rightarrow P_\phi(y, C, \tau)$, $E_\phi(y, u_n, \tau) \rightarrow E_\phi(y, C, \tau)$ and $Z_\phi(y, u_n, \tau) \rightarrow Z_\phi(y, C, \tau)$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Since C is approximatively compact with respect to D , $\{u_n\}$ has a convergent subsequence $\{u_{n_k}\}$, converging to some $z \in C$.

Since Γ is continuous and $u_{n_k} \rightarrow z$, we get $\Gamma u_{n_k} \rightarrow \Gamma z$. Consequently, y and Γz are identical.

By the definition of neutrosophic metric, using $\Gamma u_{n_k} \rightarrow \Gamma z$ and $u_{n_k} \rightarrow z$ in (11), we get

$$\begin{aligned} P_\phi(z, \Gamma z, \tau) &= P_\phi(C, D, \tau), \\ E_\phi(z, \Gamma z, \tau) &= E_\phi(C, D, \tau), \\ Z_\phi(z, \Gamma z, \tau) &= Z_\phi(C, D, \tau). \end{aligned}$$

Hence, z is a best proximity point for Γ .

Claim 3: Γ has unique best proximity point.

Suppose we can find another element z^* such that:

$$\begin{aligned} P_\phi(z^*, \Gamma z^*, \tau) &= P_\phi(C, D, \tau), \\ E_\phi(z^*, \Gamma z^*, \tau) &= E_\phi(C, D, \tau), \\ Z_\phi(z^*, \Gamma z^*, \tau) &= Z_\phi(C, D, \tau). \end{aligned}$$

Since Γ is a neutrosophic proximal contraction of second kind, for every $\tau \in (0, \infty)$ and fixed $k \in (0, 1)$, we have:

$$\begin{aligned} P_\phi(\Gamma z, \Gamma z^*, k\tau) &\geq P_\phi(\Gamma z, \Gamma z^*, \tau), \\ E_\phi(\Gamma z, \Gamma z^*, k\tau) &\leq E_\phi(\Gamma z, \Gamma z^*, \tau), \\ Z_\phi(\Gamma z, \Gamma z^*, k\tau) &\leq Z_\phi(\Gamma z, \Gamma z^*, \tau). \end{aligned}$$

Now, from the above, we get:

$$\begin{aligned} 1 &\geq P_\phi(\Gamma z, \Gamma z^*, \tau) \geq P_\phi\left(\Gamma z, \Gamma z^*, \frac{\tau}{k}\right) \geq P_\phi\left(\Gamma z, \Gamma z^*, \frac{\tau}{k^2}\right) \\ &\geq \dots \geq P_\phi\left(\Gamma z, \Gamma z^*, \frac{\tau}{k^n}\right) \rightarrow 1 \quad \text{as } n \rightarrow \infty, \\ 0 &\leq E_\phi(\Gamma z, \Gamma z^*, \tau) \leq E_\phi\left(\Gamma z, \Gamma z^*, \frac{\tau}{k}\right) \leq E_\phi\left(\Gamma z, \Gamma z^*, \frac{\tau}{k^2}\right) \\ &\leq \dots \leq E_\phi\left(\Gamma z, \Gamma z^*, \frac{\tau}{k^n}\right) \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } n \rightarrow \infty, \\ 0 &\leq Z_\phi(\Gamma z, \Gamma z^*, \tau) \leq Z_\phi\left(\Gamma z, \Gamma z^*, \frac{\tau}{k}\right) \leq Z_\phi\left(\Gamma z, \Gamma z^*, \frac{\tau}{k^2}\right) \\ &\leq \dots \leq Z_\phi\left(\Gamma z, \Gamma z^*, \frac{\tau}{k^n}\right) \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } n \rightarrow \infty. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, from the definition of a neutrosophic metric space (NMS), we get $\Gamma z = \Gamma z^*$. \square

Here, we have an example to illustrate Theorem 3.3.

Example 3.4. Example 3.2 satisfies Theorem 3.3 as well. Here, in addition, we need to verify only the contraction condition.

Claim: Γ is a neutrosophic proximal contraction of the second kind.

Step 1: Suppose we have $(0, u_1), (0, u_2), (0, x_1), (0, x_2) \in C$ such that

$$P_\phi((0, u_1), \Gamma(0, x_1), \tau) = P_\phi(C, D, \tau) = \frac{1}{2} = P_\phi((0, u_2), \Gamma(0, x_2), \tau).$$

We have to verify that $P_\phi(\Gamma(0, u_1), \Gamma(0, u_2), k\tau) \geq P_\phi(\Gamma(0, x_1), \Gamma(0, x_2), \tau)$ for some $k \in [0, 1)$.

Then $u_1 = \frac{x_1}{4}$ and $u_2 = \frac{x_2}{4}$, for all $(0, x_1), (0, x_2) \in C$. Now, consider

$$P_\phi(\Gamma(0, u_1), \Gamma(0, u_2), k\tau) = \frac{1}{1 + \left| \frac{u_1}{4} - \frac{u_2}{4} \right|},$$

and

$$P_\phi(\Gamma(0, x_1), \Gamma(0, x_2), \tau) = \frac{1}{1 + \left| \frac{x_1}{4} - \frac{x_2}{4} \right|} = \frac{1}{1 + 4 \left| \frac{u_1}{4} - \frac{u_2}{4} \right|}.$$

Hence, it holds for $k \in [0, 1)$.

Step 2: Suppose we have $(0, u_1), (0, u_2), (0, x_1), (0, x_2) \in C$ such that

$$E_\phi((0, u_1), \Gamma(0, x_1), \tau) = E_\phi(C, D, \tau) = \frac{1}{2} = E_\phi((0, u_2), \Gamma(0, x_1), \tau).$$

We have to verify that $E_\phi(\Gamma(0, u_1), \Gamma(0, u_2), k\tau) \leq E_\phi(\Gamma(0, x_1), \Gamma(0, x_2), \tau)$ for some $k \in [0, 1)$.

Then $u_1 = \frac{x_1}{4}$ and $u_2 = \frac{x_2}{4}$, for all $(0, x_1), (0, x_2) \in C$. Now, consider

$$E_\phi(\Gamma(0, u_1), \Gamma(0, u_2), k\tau) = \frac{\left| \frac{u_1}{4} - \frac{u_2}{4} \right|}{1 + \left| \frac{u_1}{4} - \frac{u_2}{4} \right|},$$

and

$$E_\phi(\Gamma(0, x_1), \Gamma(0, x_2), \tau) = \frac{\left| \frac{x_1}{4} - \frac{x_2}{4} \right|}{1 + \left| \frac{x_1}{4} - \frac{x_2}{4} \right|} = \frac{|u_1 - u_2|}{1 + |u_1 - u_2|}.$$

Hence, it holds for $k \in [0, 1)$.

Step 3: Suppose we have $(0, u_1), (0, u_2), (0, x_1), (0, x_2) \in C$ such that

$$Z_\phi((0, u_1), \Gamma(0, x_1), \tau) = Z_\phi(C, D, \tau) = 1 = Z_\phi((0, u_2), \Gamma(0, x_2), \tau).$$

We have to verify that $Z_\phi(\Gamma(0, u_1), \Gamma(0, u_2), k\tau) \leq Z_\phi(\Gamma(0, x_1), \Gamma(0, x_2), \tau)$ for some $k \in [0, 1)$.

Then $u_1 = \frac{x_1}{4}$ and $u_2 = \frac{x_2}{4}$, for all $(0, x_1), (0, x_2) \in C$. Now, consider

$$Z_\phi(\Gamma(0, u_1), \Gamma(0, u_2), k\tau) = \left| \frac{u_1}{4} - \frac{u_2}{4} \right|,$$

and

$$Z_\phi(\Gamma(0, x_1), \Gamma(0, x_2), \tau) = \left| \frac{x_1}{4} - \frac{x_2}{4} \right| = |u_1 - u_2|.$$

Hence, it holds for $k \in [0, 1)$.

Thus, Γ is a neutrosophic proximal contraction of the second kind. Now, by Theorem 3.3, Γ has a unique best proximity point $(0, 0)$ in C .

Next, we replace the continuous map Γ in Theorem 3.3 by an injective map Γ .

Theorem 3.5. *Let (C, D) be a pair of two non-empty closed subsets of a non-Archimedean neutrosophic complete metric space $(R, P_\phi, E_\phi, Z_\phi, *, \diamond)$ such that C_0 is non-empty and C is approximately compact with respect to D . Let $\Gamma : C \rightarrow D$ be a map satisfying the conditions given below:*

- (i) Γ is an injective continuous neutrosophic proximal contraction of second kind,
- (ii) $\Gamma(C_0) \subseteq D_0$.

Then, there exists a unique best proximity point $z \in C$ for Γ . That is, $P_\phi(z, \Gamma z, \tau) = P_\phi(C, D, \tau)$, $E_\phi(z, \Gamma z, \tau) = E_\phi(C, D, \tau)$, and $Z_\phi(z, \Gamma z, \tau) = Z_\phi(C, D, \tau)$. Furthermore, for any fixed element $u_0 \in C_0$, the sequence $\{u_n\}$ defined by $P_\phi(u_{n+1}, \Gamma u_n, \tau) = P_\phi(C, D, \tau)$, $E_\phi(u_{n+1}, \Gamma u_n, \tau) = E_\phi(C, D, \tau)$, and $Z_\phi(u_{n+1}, \Gamma u_n, \tau) = Z_\phi(C, D, \tau)$ has a subsequence $\{u_{n_k}\}$ which converges to the element z .

Proof. The existence of a best proximity point can be proved by following the same argument as in the proof of Theorem 3.3. The uniqueness follows from the fact that Γ is injective. \square

Remark 3.6. Here, we cannot compare Theorem 3.3 and Theorem 3.5 as the class of continuous maps and injective maps are incomparable.

Suppose the given non-self map is both neutrosophic proximal contraction of first kind as well as a neutrosophic proximal contraction of second kind, then we can remove the condition on the approximately compactness of C with respect to D and the continuity of Γ . Hence we obtain the following result.

Theorem 3.7. *Let (C, D) be a pair of two non-empty closed subsets of a non-Archimedean neutrosophic complete metric space $(R, P_\phi, E_\phi, Z_\phi, *, \diamond)$ such that C_0 is non-empty. Let $\Gamma : C \rightarrow D$ be a map satisfying the conditions given below:*

- (i) Γ is a neutrosophic proximal contraction of first kind as well as a neutrosophic proximal contraction of second kind,
- (ii) $\Gamma(C_0) \subseteq D_0$.

Then, there exists a unique best proximity point $x \in C$ for Γ . That is, $P_\phi(x, \Gamma x, \tau) = P_\phi(C, D, \tau)$, $E_\phi(x, \Gamma x, \tau) = E_\phi(C, D, \tau)$, and $Z_\phi(x, \Gamma x, \tau) = Z_\phi(C, D, \tau)$. Further, for any fixed element $u_0 \in C_0$, the sequence $\{u_n\}$, defined by $P_\phi(u_{n+1}, \Gamma u_n, \tau) = P_\phi(C, D, \tau)$, $E_\phi(u_{n+1}, \Gamma u_n, \tau) = E_\phi(C, D, \tau)$, and $Z_\phi(u_{n+1}, \Gamma u_n, \tau) = Z_\phi(C, D, \tau)$ converges to the element x .

Proof. Following the proof of Theorem 3.1, we can find a sequence $\{u_n\}$ in C satisfying the conditions given below:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} P_\phi(u_{n+1}, \Gamma u_n, \tau) &= P_\phi(C, D, \tau), \\ E_\phi(u_{n+1}, \Gamma u_n, \tau) &= E_\phi(C, D, \tau), \\ Z_\phi(u_{n+1}, \Gamma u_n, \tau) &= Z_\phi(C, D, \tau), \quad \forall n \in \mathbb{N}. \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{18}$$

As in Theorem 3.1, we have that $\{u_n\}$ is a Cauchy sequence and converges to some $x \in C$. Further, as in Theorem 3.3, we have that $\{\Gamma u_n\}$ is a Cauchy sequence and converges to some $y \in D$. Therefore, we obtain that

$$\left. \begin{aligned} P_\phi(x, y, \tau) &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} P_\phi(u_{n+1}, \Gamma u_n, \tau) = P_\phi(C, D, \tau), \\ E_\phi(x, y, \tau) &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} E_\phi(u_{n+1}, \Gamma u_n, \tau) = E_\phi(C, D, \tau), \\ Z_\phi(x, y, \tau) &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Z_\phi(u_{n+1}, \Gamma u_n, \tau) = Z_\phi(C, D, \tau). \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{19}$$

That is, $x \in C_0$. Since $\Gamma(C_0) \subseteq D_0$, we get $\Gamma x \in D_0$.

As $\Gamma x \in D_0$, $\exists z \in C_0$ such that

$$\left. \begin{aligned} P_\phi(z, \Gamma x, \tau) &= P_\phi(C, D, \tau), \\ E_\phi(z, \Gamma x, \tau) &= E_\phi(C, D, \tau), \\ Z_\phi(z, \Gamma x, \tau) &= Z_\phi(C, D, \tau). \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{20}$$

From (18), (20), and since T is a neutrosophic proximal contraction of first kind, we have

$$\left. \begin{aligned} P_\phi(u_{n+1}, z, k\tau) &\geq P_\phi(u_n, x, \tau), \\ E_\phi(u_{n+1}, z, k\tau) &\leq E_\phi(u_n, x, \tau), \\ Z_\phi(u_{n+1}, z, k\tau) &\leq Z_\phi(u_n, x, \tau), \quad \forall n \in \mathbb{N}. \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{21}$$

By the definition of neutrosophic metric and using $u_n \rightarrow x$ in (21), we get

$$\left. \begin{aligned} 1 &\geq P_\phi(x, z, k\tau) \geq P_\phi(x, x, \tau) = 1, \\ 0 &\leq E_\phi(x, z, k\tau) \leq E_\phi(x, x, \tau) = 0, \\ 0 &\leq Z_\phi(x, z, k\tau) \leq Z_\phi(x, x, \tau) = 0. \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{22}$$

Hence, we get $x = z$. From (20), it follows that x is a best proximity point for Γ . The uniqueness can be proved similarly to Theorem 3.1. \square

4. Conclusions

Best proximity point theory is important in nonlinear analysis and optimization as it provides solutions to problems where fixed points do not exist. In many real-world situations, such as in economics, engineering, and computer science, we often deal with mappings between two non-overlapping sets where a traditional fixed point is not possible. Best proximity point

theory addresses this by finding points in one set that are as close as possible to their images in the other set, minimizing the distance between them. This concept generalizes fixed point theory and is crucial for solving constrained optimization problems, variational inequalities, and equilibrium models where exact solutions are unattainable but best approximate solutions are meaningful and applicable.

In this study, we generalized the notion of best proximity points for non-self mappings within the framework of neutrosophic complete metric spaces. Furthermore, we established results regarding the existence and uniqueness of best proximity points for neutrosophic proximal contractions of both the first and second kind. To illustrate and validate our main findings, we also presented relevant examples.

Therefore, in the context of neutrosophic metric spaces, we have presented the fundamental theory regarding the existence of best proximity point for a non-self map. Motivated by our findings, one can extend the results to weaker contractions, more generalized spaces and even by changing the kind of non-self maps taken into consideration, and hence these findings can be generalized in a subsequent study. In addition, our result will be helpful for building the theory to find application in the field of non-linear analysis, differential equations, optimization, game theory and even fractal theory.

Grants and Funding: The first author (A.S.U) would like to thank UGC for providing financial support in the form of Savitribai Jyotirao Phule Single Girl Child Fellowship (SJSGC) under the grand no: (82-7/2022(SA-III)).

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

References

1. Smarandache, F. (1998). Neutrosophy: neutrosophic probability, set, and logic: analytic synthesis & synthetic analysis.
2. Kirişçi, M., & Şimşek, N. (2020). Neutrosophic metric spaces. *Mathematical Sciences*, 14(3), 241-248. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s40096-020-00335-8>
3. Kirişçi, M., Şimşek, N., & Akyiğit, M. (2021). Fixed point results for a new metric space. *Mathematical Methods in the Applied Sciences*, 44(9). <https://doi.org/10.1002/mma.6189>
4. Akram, M., Ishtiaq, U., Ahmad, K., Lazăr, T. A., Lazăr, V. L., & Guran, L. (2024). Some generalized neutrosophic metric spaces and fixed point results with applications. *Symmetry*, 16(8), 965. <https://doi.org/10.3390/sym16080965>
5. Saleem, N., Ahmad, K., Ishtiaq, U., & De la Sen, M. (2023). Multivalued neutrosophic fractals and Hutchinson-Barnsley operator in neutrosophic metric space. *Chaos, Solitons & Fractals*, 172, 113607. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chaos.2023.113607>
6. Ishtiaq, U., Kattan, D. A., Ahmad, K., Lazăr, T. A., Lazăr, V. L., & Guran, L. (2023). On intuitionistic fuzzy N b metric space and related fixed point results with application to nonlinear fractional differential equations. *Fractal and Fractional*, 7(7), 529. <https://doi.org/10.3390/fractalfract7070529>

A. Sreelakshmi Unni and V. Pragadeeswarar, Existence and uniqueness of best proximity point in non-Archimedean neutrosophic complete metric space

7. Ishtiaq, U., Javed, K., Uddin, F., Sen, M. D. L., Ahmed, K., & Ali, M. U. (2021). Fixed point results in orthogonal neutrosophic metric spaces. *Complexity*, 2021(1), 2809657. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/2809657>
8. Shatanawi, W., Abodayeh, K., & Mukheimer, A. (2018). Some fixed point theorems in extended b-metric spaces. *UPB Scientific Bulletin, Series A: Applied Mathematics and Physics*, 80(4), 71-78.
9. Shatanawi, W., & Shatnawi, T. A. (2023). Some fixed point results based on contractions of new types for extended b-metric spaces. *Aims Math*, 8(5), 10929-10946. <https://doi.org/10.3934/math.2023554>
10. Alamgir, N., Kiran, Q., Aydi, H., & Mukheimer, A. (2019). A Mizoguchi–Takahashi type fixed point theorem in complete extended b-metric spaces. *Mathematics*, 7(5), 478. <https://doi.org/10.3390/math7050478>
11. Eldred, A. A., & Veeramani, P. (2006). Existence and convergence of best proximity points. *Journal of Mathematical Analysis and Applications*, 323(2), 1001-1006. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmaa.2005.10.081>
12. Al-Thagafi, M. A., & Shahzad, N. (2009). Convergence and existence results for best proximity points. *Nonlinear Analysis: Theory, Methods & Applications*, 70(10), 3665-3671. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.na.2008.07.022>
13. Basha, S. S., & Veeramani, P. (1997). Best proximity pairs and best approximations. *Acta Scientiarum Mathematicarum*, 63(1), 289-300.
14. Kirk, W. A., Reich, S., & Veeramani, P. (2003). Proximinal retracts and best proximity pair theorems. <https://doi.org/10.1081/NFA-120026380>
15. Basha, S. S., & Veeramani, P. (2000). Best proximity pair theorems for multifunctions with open fibres. *Journal of Approximation Theory*, 103(1), 119-129. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jath.1999.3415>
16. Sankar Raj, V., & Veeramani, P. (2009). Best proximity pair theorems for relatively nonexpansive mappings. *Applied General Topology*, 10(1), 21-28. <https://doi.org/10.4995/agt.2009.1784>
17. Sadiq Basha, S. (2011). Best proximity points: optimal solutions. *Journal of optimization theory and applications*, 151(1), 210-216. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10957-011-9869-4>
18. Basha, S. S. (2012). Best proximity point theorems: an exploration of a common solution to approximation and optimization problems. *Applied Mathematics and Computation*, 218(19), 9773-9780. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amc.2012.03.033>
19. Pragadeeswarar, V., & Marudai, M. (2013). Best proximity points: approximation and optimization in partially ordered metric spaces. *Optimization Letters*, 7(8), 1883-1892. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11590-012-0529-x>
20. Unni, A. S., & Pragadeeswarar, V. (2025). Proximal iterated function systems using cyclic Meir-Keeler contractions and an application to fractal theory. *Fixed Point Theory and Algorithms for Sciences and Engineering*, 2025(1), 3. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13663-025-00784-7>
21. Unni, A. S., & Pragadeeswarar, V. (2025). Existence and uniqueness of fractals in fuzzy metric space via best proximity point. *Rendiconti del Circolo Matematico di Palermo (Serie II)*, 74, art. 160. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12215-025-01269-7>
22. George, A., & Veeramani, P. (1994). On some results in fuzzy metric spaces. *Fuzzy sets and systems*, 64(3), 395-399. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-0114\(94\)90162-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-0114(94)90162-7)
23. Sowndrarajan, S., Jeyaraman, M., & Smarandache, F. (2020). Fixed point results for contraction theorems in neutrosophic metric spaces (Vol. 36). *Infinite Study*.

Received: Feb 7, 2025. Accepted: Aug 15, 2025